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Volumetric Modulated Arc Therapy vs. 3D conformal radiotherapy in treatment of locally advanced cervical carcinoma

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Introduction: Radiotherapy/chemoradiotherapy is often initial and definitive treatment mode for locally advanced cervical carcinoma. Advanced radiation techniques allow dose escalation to the desired target volume with greater sparing of surrounding organs at risk. The aim of this study is to examine whether there are statistically significant differences in clinical outcomes between patients treated with VMAT and 3D conformal radiation technique.

Materials and methods: A retrospective analysis of 61 patients treated for primary cervical carcinoma ranging from FIGO Ib-IIIc was performed. 40 patients were treated with 3D conformal radiotherapy and 21 were treated with Volumetric Modulated Arc Therapy (VMAT). Evaluated parameters included complete clinical response, which was assessed based on a follow-up pelvic MRI, average progression free survival and 3-year overall survival. The Chi-square test and the Mann-Whitney test were used to analyze the collected data.

Results: Statistically significant difference with respect to 3-year overall survival was achieved in favor of patients treated with VMAT radiation technique (90,47% vs. 62,5%; $p = 0,021$), while the average progression free survival was 14,67 and 10,18 months, respectively.

Conclusion: This study has shown a trend toward improved survival of patients who were treated with VMAT, compared to those treated with 3D conformal technique.

Key words: Volumetric Modulated Arc, 3D conformal, radiotherapy, cervical carcinoma

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